

Human Rights Movements in India

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ABSTRACT

The human rights movement in India began under the Emergency Rule from 1975 to 1977 and continued to grow after the Emergency. Two key tendencies emerged: civil liberties concerns and rights-based viewpoints. Over the last 35 years, the human rights movement has benefited from collective wisdom gleaned from the tribal movement, women's liberation movement, child rights movement, dalit movement, and battles of the differently abled. The state and mainstream institutions have had love-hate relationships with various sorts of human rights groups throughout history.

Key Words: Civil liberties, women's movement, dalit movement, civil society

Introduction

Human rights have gained recognition in India in the late 20th century, driven by social movements. It is self-evident that this interest in human rights stems from the widespread deprivation of life and liberty during the emergency (1975-1977). Some of the main images that have endured are mass arrests of opposition leaders and targeted arrests of anyone who may pose a risk to an authoritarian authority.¹ Rajan's involuntary abduction in Kerala represents more than just the evils of unchecked authority.

Forced evictions at Delhi's 'Turkman Gate' conjure up images of large-scale razing of low-income residents' homes and their displacement to the city's outskirts. The brutal mass sterilization campaign had a lasting impact on my memory. The civil liberties movement was a result of the emergency. The civil liberties movement's agenda included arbitrary imprisonment, custodial brutality, jails, and the utilization of the legal process. Peasant movements, tribal movements, dalit movements, backward caste movements, women's movements, working-class movements, student movements, middle-class movements, and environmental movements have all raised concerns about human rights during the last thirty years.

Contribution of Women's Movement to Human Rights Movement

In 1980, a nationwide anti-rape movement led in the formation and growth of independent women's organizations in various Indian cities and villages. To address rape, domestic violence, and dowry harassment against women, these groups recognized the need for institutional structures based on feminist principles of solidarity, mutual counselling, and sisterhood to provide long-term support.² In India's criminal judicial system, it was necessary for these groups to create relationships with the police in order to provide prompt relief to women who had experienced abuse.

The condition of women in detention houses and the Nari Niketans was so disgusting and cruel that they could not be trusted with women's rehabilitation. In reality, many women who had suffered at their hands sought the newly formed women's clubs.

Women campaigners had to face with a victim-baiting mentality, double standards of sexual morality, sexist insults, and ill humor from police, legal officials, and public hospital employees. They faced prejudices based on class, caste, and community throughout their journey. These led to a conflict between women's organizations and established institutions.

Over time, they recognized the need for specific alternatives such as legislation reforms, intervention methods, and staff training to promote attitude change.³ For public education, literature published in a compelling style was essential. It was required to create audio-visual content in order to reach a larger number of individuals. Professional entities and educational institutions approached these groups to better grasp the women's question. During the 1980s and 1990s, 'special interest groups' emerged to focus on agitation, propaganda, media monitoring, awareness raising, cultural alternatives, publications, research, bookstalls, and legal aid. These groups played complimentary roles in each other's growth, however the process was not always easy.

Sexual Harassment at Workplace

During the 1990s, the most notorious survivor of horrific workplace gang rape was a Rajasthan state government employee who attempted to prevent child marriage as part of her duties as a Women Development Programme worker. The feudal patriarchy, incensed by the 'guts' of, in their words, 'a humble woman from a poor and wretched town', determined to teach her a lesson by repeatedly raping her (Samhita, 2001).⁴ Despite an exceedingly humiliating legal struggle in the Rajasthan High Court, the rape victim did not receive justice, and the rapists, 'educated and high caste rich men', were permitted to walk free. Vishakha, a women's rights group, filed a public interest litigation before India's Supreme Court (Combat Law 2003).

Sexual harassment, as defined in the Supreme Court guidelines (Vishakha vs State of Rajasthan, August 1997), includes unwanted sexual behavior such as physical contact, demands for sexual favors, sexually coloured remarks, showing pornography, and other unwelcome physical, verbal, or nonverbal conduct of a sexual nature, such as leering, telling dirty jokes, and making sexual remarks about a person's body.

Dalit Rights Movement

Dalit struggles have maintained caste discrimination in the public spotlight. As the movement moves beyond untouchability, violence against dalits has increased. However, dalits continue to resist quiet and challenge conventional caste hierarchies. For example, in Bihar, caste armies are becoming more prevalent. Another case is the killing of dalit panchayat leaders in Melmzhuvur, Tamil Nadu. A third example is police fire on dalits who were observed protesting their persecution in Tamil Nadu's southern edge.⁵ Priyanka Bhutmange and her family members were gang raped, tortured, and brutally murdered in Khairlanji, Maharashtra.

A third example is police fire on dalits who were observed protesting their persecution in Tamil Nadu's southern edge. Priyanka Bhutmange and her family members were gang raped, tortured, and brutally murdered in Khairlanji, Maharashtra. The issue of manual scavenging has been addressed in legislative and legal campaigns, and efforts have been made to overcome public resistance to acknowledge the existence of untouchability. Meanwhile, groups working on dalit issues are attempting to internationalize entrenched caste prejudice by influencing the World Conference against Racism's agenda.

Dalits face severe abuses, atrocities, and crimes in India. According to official Indian crime statistics from 2001-2005, there were 27 atrocities against dalits per day, 13 murders per week, five homes or possessions burned, six kidnapped or abducted, three women raped daily, eleven beaten daily, and one crime committed against a dalit every eighteen minutes.

Dalit Women and Human Rights

The social, economic, and political power imbalances in caste and patriarchy have a distinct impact on 'untouchable women' compared to other women and men. These dynamics combine to expose individuals to more physical and sexual abuse, as well as increasing labor exploitation. Together, these prevent untouchable women from accessing and controlling assets and resources.

It does not acknowledge their social or economic impact. It limits their options and prospects, placing them at the bottom of all development metrics. Exclusion and prejudice perpetuate disdain and indignity towards untouchable women by both males and non-untouchable women.

India is a democratic country that has signed most of the main United Nations human rights treaties. These accords provide equal rights for men and women.⁶ As a signatory to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), India's government has an additional responsibility to ensure women's rights are respected. It is widely acknowledged in international law that governments must do more than simply establish legislation to defend human rights. The Indian government is responsible for ensuring women's rights through policies and financial measures. It is also responsible for punishing people who commit caste-based violence and prejudice.

The Government of India, as a modern country with a developing economy, has the resources to meet its duties. The National Campaign for Dalit Human Rights (NCDHR) is a coalition of Dalit human rights activists, civil society organizations, journalists, and academics dedicated to ending caste-based discrimination and 'untouchability' practices that deny human rights and dignity to 170 million Indian citizens one-sixth of the country's population.

Current Movements and Campaigns

Movements for self-determination, militancy, dissent, and the Naxalite movement have led to exceptional measures, prompting human rights groups to protest and question. TADA is an example (Singh, 2007). The Armed Forces Special Powers Act (AFSPA) remains. Human rights violations, including deaths, disappearances, and inefficient legal systems, are common in combat zones. Human rights jurisprudence has evolved in various circumstances. Networking and supporting each other during disputes and campaigns is not uncommon.

There are hints of the establishment or presence of a 'human rights community' in this. Groups and movements working on tourism, forest dwellers' rights, civil liberties, displacement, women's rights, and environment have found a common voice in protesting nuclear blasts in May 1999 and condemning attacks on the filming of 'Water', which had undeniable communal overtones.⁷ Bridges have been built between causes, resulting in an interconnected community of interests. As the scope of rights has broadened, conflicts between rights have begun to emerge. As a result, rights have become more important. Priorities have frequently been determined by the entity responsible for determining them sometimes environmental organizations, sometimes labor, and sometimes the court.

Human Rights Education

The Indian intelligentsia recognized the importance of human rights education after experiencing witch-hunting during the emergency era. Those who opposed the emergency rule used the slogan 'Democracy vs Dictatorship'. In response, supporters of the emergency declared 'Discipline vs Democracy'. During the 19th month emergency rule in 1975-1976, the majority of educated and articulate Indians were betrayed, with the famous slogan "Hum Hamara Munh sirf Khane ke liye aur ubasleneke liye Kholate hai" referring to eating and yawning. The Mumbai Initiative for Human Rights Education (MIHRE) organizes workshops for schools and colleges to promote human rights awareness among teachers and students.

Human Rights and Pro-poor Development

Recognizing poverty as a violation of human rights is crucial for policymakers, including governments, funders, international organizations, and lawmakers.⁸ It is a condition caused by chronic situations in which individuals, families, and entire communities are deprived, and as a result, they may suffer from one or more of the following conditions: homelessness, a lack of education, ill health, disability, a lack of opportunities for livelihood, and an inability to access public services or even justice itself (Muralidhar, 2004). Each of these conditions violates internationally recognized human rights standards, including the right to adequate housing, education, health facilities, work, livelihood, equal access to public services, and the right to seek justice (Mishra, 2008).

Right to Food

In 2001, a People's Union for Civil Liberties (PUCL) petition in the Supreme Court on hunger in Rajasthan sparked the Right to Food Campaign. The campaign aimed to make the Right to Food a fundamental right, convert existing schemes into entitlements, address large-scale malnutrition and chronic hunger, and secure employment as a fundamental right.⁹ The Right to Food Campaign focuses on implementing nutrition-related schemes, introducing cooked mid-day meals in primary schools, reforming and expanding the public distribution system (PDS), recognizing the right to work, particularly in drought-affected areas, and providing social security for the poor.¹⁰

Right to Health

The Indian branch of People's Health Assembly (PHA) is constantly working for the right to health. PHA organizes public hearings and news conferences, advocates for improved health budgets, releases statements, and negotiates with the government. It is crucial to understand PHA's history. In 1978, world leaders signed the Alma Ata Declaration, which pledged 'Health for All by 2000'.¹¹ However, this pledge was not taken seriously and was later overlooked in health policy talks.

As the year 2000 neared, it looked that governments throughout the world had silently forgotten 'Health for All by 2000'. To remind people of this neglected pledge, the First People's Health Assembly was held in Savar, Bangladesh, in December 2000. The PHA was a global gathering of people's movements and other non-governmental civil society groups to renew the commitment for Health for All and ensure that governments took this promise seriously.¹² PHA has made significant contributions to the development of global solidarity and the collaboration of people's movements and organizations striving to enhance people's health in the context of globalization policies.

Conclusion

The character and organization of the human rights community have altered dramatically since India's post-emergency period, when the first human rights movement emerged following independence from British colonial authority. The emergency period (1975-1977) heightened the middle class's commitment to fighting for human rights as they faced a shortfall in democracy for the first time in the post-independence era. People's groups promote human rights through both top-down and bottom-up ways.

We must demand more openness from the government in dealing with militancy, which means treating all fundamentalist and fascist movements equally. Those found breaking the law and committing crimes must be punished, but only in conformity with the law and human rights norms. Using politics of fear for short-term political benefits can lead to corruption within investigative agencies and damage the criminal justice system.

Human rights groups combat religious chauvinism and market fundamentalism through political and intellectual means. They promote secular humanism and express the concerns of those who have been repressed, stifled, or brutalised. Their dedication to human rights encompasses both individual and collective rights.

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